

ONOMASTIC UNITS USED IN AJIZ'S "DIVAN"

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The onomastic units that reflect the history of the Azerbaijani people are an integral part of the vocabulary of our language. Onomastic units are closely related to the past, lifestyle of the people. Onomastic units are one of the main language tools that reflect the national landscape of each nation.

Onomastic units are widely used in fiction. In linguistics, this field that studies onomastic units is called poetic onomastics. Here, mainly the fictional works, their characters, the names of the places where the events are described, their stylistic features, the increase of the idea-artistic impact of the work, etc. are studied (2, p. 50).

One of the interesting aspects of poetic onomastics is related to the transformation of onomastic units into poetic means and conveying metaphorical meaning.

The onomastic units of most nations of the world have been used in Azerbaijani literature since ancient times. This helps us to collect enough rich material for mutual study of those onomastic units.

Onomastic lexis dominates in Ajiz's "Divan". So, in this sense, the study of stylistic features of anthroponyms and toponyms is of special interest.

Keywords: onomastic, Ajiz's "Divan", anthroponyms, toponyms.

INTRODUCTION:

"Anthroponym" being in the meaning of human, is a combination of the Greek words "anthropos" and "onim". "Anthroponym" means a human name. The term anthroponymics is a field of onomastics, which studies the formation laws of anthroponyms, their place in the system of name, their development, interaction with other names, lexical-semantic and grammatical features (5, p.50).

Anthroponyms are groups of words that occupy an important place in the onomastic system of the Azerbaijani language, are lexically-semantically rich and enrich the vocabulary. Unlike other lexical units, anthroponyms have a concrete meaning as personal names, but they also have a poetic function in fiction (3, p. 40).

The scope of persons' names in Ajiz's "Divan" are wide. It should be noted that every person's name used in the work has public significance. In the work, the poet often referred to historical figures and heroes, legendary names that became famous in Eastern literature due to pure love or heroism. The special names used by the poet in the language of the work are not only for naming, but also have a poetic character. During the study, the anthroponyms used in the Ajiz's language have conventionally been included in the research according to several groups. The conventionality of the division is based on the fact that the name of a legendary person can also sometimes be accepted as a fictional character.

1) Names of shahs, sultans, rulers, titles

Ali Osman(آل عثمان)-the Ottoman dynasty.

Aghakhan(آغاخان)-a title given to the leaders of the community in the Ismailiyya sect.

Alp-Arslan(الپ ارسلان)-Sultan of Seljuk. He made military campaigns to Transcaucasia and Central Asia, defeated and captured the Byzantine emperor Diogenes. He added the lands of Byzantium in Asia Minor to

his country. He was killed during a military campaign to Mavarannahr.

Bahman(بهمن)-He is one of the kings of Iran who lived and ruled in the 5th century BC. His real name was Ardashir.

Bubakri-Siddiq(بوبکر صدیق)-the first caliph of the Rashidi caliphs. Alluding to Abu Bakr Siddig.

Buzurg Ummid(بزرگ امید)-the judge of the Nizari Ismailis in Alamut.

Javanshir(جوانشیر)-Ibrahim Khalil Khan Javanshir. Khan II of the Karabakh Khanate.

Jam (Jamshid)(جم، جمشید)-the ruler of Iran. According to the legend, he was the Shah of Iran for 700 years and peace reigned for a long time in his period. According to the legend, his real name was Jam. "Shid" means the strings of the sun. The word "Jamshid" means "combined with the strings of the sun". According to the legend, he had a glass (cam) and he saw the events of the world in that glass. The expression "Cami-Cam" is also attributed to Jamshid. Mainly in fiction, it is used as a symbol of joy and life, wine cup.

Dara(دارا)-the ruler of the Achaemenid dynasty in Iran. He reigned in Iran before the III era. He was defeated by Alexander the Great.

Ardashir(اردشیر)-the fifth ruler of the Achaemenid dynasty.

Afrasiyab(افراسیاب)-legendary person. According to the ancient history of Iranians, he is the grandson of Tur. He is considered one of the great rulers of Turan, named in honor of that Tur.

Ayaz(ایاز)-Sultan Mahmud Ghaznavi's favorite slave.

Faruq(فاروق)-the epithet of the Second Khalifa Umar bin al-Khattab.

Fathalishah(فتحعلی شاه قاجار)-shah of Iran from the Qajar dynasty. During the reign of Fath-Ali Shah, Iran became an expansion of Russia, unequal agreements were concluded with France, England and Russia.

Faridun (Firidun)(فریدون)-He is a legendary king in ancient Iranian mythology. He is one of the heroes of the “Shahnameh” epic. He is considered the grandson of Jamshid who is one of the kings of Iran, and the sixth ruler of the Pishdadian dynasty. In Eastern literature, Fereydu is a symbol of greatness and wealth.

Gudarz(گودرز)-names of two heroes from Iran's heroic era. 1) son of knight Qarin, grandson of Kaveh. 2) grandson of famous knight Giv and son of Kashvad.

Hushang(هوشنگ)-The second king of the legendary Pishdadian dynasty.

Khosrov Nushiravan(خسرو نوشیروان)-Sassanid king. In classical oriental literature, he is shown as a fair ruler. Hero of Nizami Ganjavi's poem “Khosrow and Shirin”.

Khosrov khan(خوسرو خان)-deputy of Rasht.

Khosrov Parviz(خسرو پرویز)-the son of the Shah of Iran, who belonged to the Sassanid dynasty. While Khosrow Parviz, the successor of Hormuz, was in Barda, Bahram Chubin of Persian origin staged a coup with the Persian feudal lords. He had Hormuz's eyes gouged out and dethroned him, and announced to the world that Hormuz's eye was gouged out by Khosrow Parviz. He casts this slander on Khosrow Parviz so that he cannot take the throne.

Isfandiyar(اسفندیار)-the son of Goshtasp, one of the Shahs of the Kayanian dynasty of Iran. One of the heroes of Ferdowsi's “Shahnameh”. He was thrown into prison by his father and eventually killed by Rostam's double head arrow.

Kavyan(کویان)-The official and sacred flag of the ancient Iranians, consisting of the leather apron of Kaveh the Blacksmith, and later decorated with jewels.

Karimkhan Zand(کریمخان زند)-Iranian ruler who was in power in 1763-1779.

Kayumars(کیومرث)-According to legend, he was the first king of the Pishdadian dynasty, who established the kingdom for the first time in Iran. Its translation means “a big man” in Zand language.

Kasra(کسرا)-a common epithet given to Anushirvan of the Sassanid dynasty of Iran and the Shahs of Iran who succeeded him.

Keyqubad(کیقباد)-The legendary ruler of Iran, the founder of the Kayanian dynasty. The expression “key” added to the beginning of the names of the Kayanian rulers was used in the meaning of shah. In works of art, it is mainly given as a sign of mortality.

Keykhosrov(کی خسرو)-The third ruler of the Kayanian dynasty, Siavash's son born to Farangis, daughter of Turanian ruler Afrasiab. He is considered one of the greatest kings who took the throne after avenging his father.

Qajar (قاجار) - Agha Mohammad Shah Qajar, the founder of the Qajar dynasty in Iran. As a result of the bloody wars for power after the assassination of Nadir Shah, he took the throne and declared himself king in 1796.

Kipchak Khan(قپچاقخان)-He is considered the father of the Kipchak tribe. He fought against the Georgians for the Alinja fortress and liberated the fortress.

Iskandar of Macedonia(اسکندر)-The outstanding warlord and statesman of the world, the king of Mace-

donia. Student of Aristotle. Nizami Ganjavi spoke extensively about his life and military trips in his work “Iskandarnameh”. In literature, he is also known as Iskandar Dhu al-Qarnayn.

Manuchohr(منوچهر)-VII Shah of the Pishdadian dynasty in Iran and grandson of Iraj. Manuchohr is also the son of Afridun Shirvanshah I.

Mahinbanu(مهین بانو)-She was the ruler of Barda and Aran. Its meaning is “great lady”. Her real name is Shamira.

Mirza Nabikhan(میرزا نبی خان)-public figure of Iran.

Mir İmad Hasani(میر عماد حسینی)-A famous calligrapher who lived during Shah Abbas's time.

Mustafa khan(مصطفی خان)-Shamakhi's Khan (1791-1820). He resisted the Iranian troops during the Qajar's campaign. In 1796, he was removed from power due to a disagreement with the commander of the Russian troops in Azerbaijan, General V.A.Zubov, and was replaced by his cousin Gasim. After the withdrawal of Russian troops from Azerbaijan, he took power again. Mustafa Khan received the rank of general after the Shamakhi Khanate was annexed to Russia.

Muzaffaraddin shah (مظفر دین شاه)-the son of Naser al-Din Shah from the Qajar dynasty. He was the governor of Azerbaijan for a long time. He lived in Tabriz.

Nadir(نادر)-He was a descendant of the Afshars and reigned in Iran in 1736-47.

Nurpasha(نورپاشا)-Ihsan Nuri Pasha is a famous soldier who served in the Turkish army. Later, he became one of the defenders of Kurdistan.

Nushiravan(نوشیروان)-Sassanid king. In Eastern literature, he is symbolized as a wise, fair ruler. He is the hero of genius Nizami Ganjavi's poem “Khosrow and Shirin”.

Pashang(پشنگ)-Fereydu's brother, Manuchehr's father.

Rustam(رستم)-One of the legendary heroes of Iran. Probably, in the first half of the first millennium BC, he was the head of one of the Sak tribes living in the territory of present-day Sistan.

Sayfalmulk(سیف الملوک)-He is the son of the king of Egypt in the tales of One Thousand and One Nights. In Arabic it means the sword of royalty.

Sipand(سپند)-the name of one of Alexander's knights.

Shah Mahmud(شاه محمود)-24th Ottoman sultan.

Sheikh Ali Mirza(شیخ علی میرزا)-the 9th son of Fath-Ali Shah Qajar, known by the epithet “Sheikh ol-Molouk”.

Shantil(شنطیل)-A king of India who came for helping to Afrasiab. In some sources, it is given by the name of Shangul. It is shown in both forms in the copies of the work that we have.

Toghrul(طغرل)-the founder and first sultan of the Great Seljuk State, being from the Qiniq tribe of the Oghuz province.

Tur(تور)-the fifth king of the Pishdadian dynasty of Iran. Tur is considered the great grandfather of Iranians and Turks. In some sources, the expression Turan is associated with the word Tur.

Zarir(زرير)-According to legend, the Iranian knight was also the brother of Goshtasp.

Zohhak(ضحاك)-According to Iranian legend, he was the fifth king of the Pishdadian dynasty. Because he was an Arab, he was also called "Zahhak-i Tazi". In Eastern literature, Zahhak is considered as a symbol of oppression and cruelty.

Religious and religio-mythic anthroponyms

Abbas(عباس)-Hazrat Abbas. Grandson of the Prophet. Hazrat Abbas is the first of four sons born from the marriage of Imam Ali (a.s.) with a woman named Ummul-Banin. He was born in 26 AH.

Abbas(عباس)- The real name of the Prophet Muhammad's (pbuh) uncle. The Abbasid caliphate is associated with his name.

Adam(آدم)-According to religion, the first man created by God.

Ali Aba(آل عبا)- the family of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) is meant.

Ali-athar(آل اطهار)-Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) and his pure family.

Buzar(بوذر)-Abuzar, one of the companions of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh).

Bilqeys(بليقيس)-According to religion, the ruler who was in power in the city of Saba in the 10th century BC. The woman who later became the wife of Prophet Suleiman. His real name is Balqis. Arabs adapted this name to their language. She is described as an intelligent woman in Eastern literature.

Jabril(جبريل)-One of the closest angels to the Prophet (pbuh). He is the linking man between God and his heralds. He brought the holy books from heaven to earth.

Abulqasim(ابوالقاسم)-Prophet Muhammad's kunya (pbuh).

Ali Asghar(على اصغر)-Imam Husayn's youngest son who was martyred in Karbala.

Ahmad(احمد)-Epithet of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh).

Ahriman(اهريمن)-God of evil in the religion of fire worship. As if night and darkness are at his disposal.

Ahli-beyt(اهل بيت)-pure family of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh).

Ali Akbar(على اكبر)-Imam Husayn's (a) son who was martyred in Karbala.

Ali(على)-Ali ibn Abutalib is the cousin of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) and the spouse of his daughter Fatima (pbuh). He was one of the first converts to Islam and participated in all Muslim processions. He is the first imam of the Shiites.

Ahmadi-Mahmud(احمدو محمود)-Epithet of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh).

Amiral-mominin(امير المومنين)-It expresses the meaning of believers' amir. It is the epithet of Imam Ali (as).

Ansar(انصار)-The name given to the people of Medina after the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) moved to Medina. They helped the Prophet (pbuh) a lot in the spread of Islam.

Alminnatullillah(المنتنة لله)-Only, it's thanked to God.

Aliyyi-Imran(على عمران)-One of the epithets of Abu Talib, Imam Ali's (a.s) father.

Fatima(فاطمة)-Daughter of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh), Imam Ali's (a.s) wife.

Fattah(فتاح)-It is one of the names of God. From a lexical point of view, the expression Fattah, which means "to open something, to judge between two sides, to help one and win", means the one who opens the doors of good.

Hashim(هاشم)-It is the name of Hashem, the great-grandfather of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). In classical literature, it is expressed as a symbol of purity, holiness, and nobility.

Hablulmatin(حبل المتين)-"Hablulmatin" is a word of the Quran, which means "a strong rope stretching to God". Religious people call the prayer "habbul-matin".

Heydari-Safdar(حيدر صفدر)-One of the epithets of Hazrat Ali (a.s).

Hasan və Huseyn(حسن و حسين)-Grandsons of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh), children of Ali (a.s) and Fatima (a.s). Hasan was poisoned at the age of 45, and Husayn was killed by Yezid in Karbala desert.

Hazrat İsmail(حضرت اسماعيل)-Prophet Ibrahim's (a.s) son.

Hujjatullah(حجة الله)-translated from Arabic, "hujjat" means evidence, proof. For example, proof that someone is right is called hujjet. Hujjatullah is an epithet usually attributed to prophets and imams.

Khalilullah(خليل الله)-one of the epithets of Prophet Ibrahim (a.s). It means close to God.

Khallaq(خالق)-"Khaliq" derived from the root "Khalaqa" means the creator. Islamic scholars explain the meaning of the name "Khaliq", which is one of the 99 names of God, as "the one who creates according to his will". The word "Khallaq" which means "Creator" is also used in two verses of the Quran.

Khalifa(خليفة)-A title given to a person who is the head of state after the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) in the Islamic state in the sense of follower of a person, succeeding him, representing him.

Keyrunnisa(خير النساء)-epithet of Fatima Zahra (pbuh). It means the best of women.

Khizir(خضر)-one of the legendary prophets. It is also called Khizir Nabi in fairy tales. Khizir's going into darkness and drinking from the legendary water of life and gaining immortality are sometimes associated with the legendary Alexander and sometimes with the prophet Ilyas.

Ibrahim(ابراهيم)-According to the Quran, he is considered the great-grandfather of Muslims and Jews and one of the predecessors of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). Prophet Ibrahim's grave is in Palestine. According to legend, he was thrown into the fire by Nimrod, the ruler of Babylon, because he opposed paganism. But the bonfire flourished and Prophet Ibrahim (pbuh) was saved. This is considered his prophetic miracle.

Isa(عيسى)-He is considered the prophet of Christians. In the East, the term Messiah is used as a synonym for Jesus (pbuh).

Israfil(اسرافيل)-one of God's angels. It is used in the text as "Serafil". God appointed him to raise the dead from the graves on the Day of Resurrection by playing the trumpet.

Kovsar(كوثر)-a name of a spring in heaven according to Islam. The word *Abi-Kovsar* is also taken from here.

Qasimul-arzaq(قاسم الارزاق)-one of the 99 names of God. It means "the one who divides sustenance correctly".

Qasim(قاسم)- Imam Hasan's (a.s.) son. He was martyred in Karbala.

Maryam(مريم)-Mother of Prophet Jesus (pbuh). According to religious belief, she was a virgin when she gave birth to Jesus.

Musa(موسى)-He is one of the most mentioned and talked about prophets in the Quran. He is Imran's son, a descendant of the Prophet Yusuf. The Torah, one of the divine books, was revealed to him. He received the epithet *Kalimullah* (the one who talks to God) because of his *munajat* with God on Mount Tur. The name *Musay-Imran* is also found in the work.

Mustafa(مصطفى)-one of the epithets of Prophet Muhammad (pbuh).

Mikail(مكاييل)- According to Islam, there are four great angels who are close to God: *Jabrail*, *Mikail*, *Azrail*, *Israfil*. *Mikail* always looks sad because he is disappointed that people have strayed from the right path. In religious books, he is described as a tall, gray-haired angel. *Mikail* distributes the provisions given by God to people.

Ruqayya(رقية)-granddaughter of the Prophet (pbuh). Imam Husayn's daughter

Sara(سارا)-Prophet Ibrahim's wife

Safura(صفورا)-Prophet Muas's wife. Prophet Shuayb's daughter.

Sakina(سكينة)-granddaughter of the Prophet (pbuh). Imam Husayn's daughter

Suleiman(سليمان)- According to the Bible, the owner of the kingdom was distinguished by his extraordinary wisdom. According to religious legend, he knew the language of animals and birds. His name is also mentioned in the Quran.

Suhayl(سهيل)-He was the first person from Yemen to believe in Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). This person from Yemen is said to be too black.

Shir-i Khuda(شير خدا)-God's lion. One of the epithets of Hazrat Ali (a.s.)

Shir-i Yazdan(شير يزدان)-one of the epithets of Hazrat Ali (a.s.). It means lion of God.

Shimr(شمر)-one of the army commanders sent by Yazid against the supporters of Imam Husayn (a.s.). He was one of those who killed Imam Husayn. It is shown as a negative character in Eastern literature.

Tavaf(طواف)-going around the Kaaba during the Hajj pilgrimage.

Tuba(طوبى)-a superstitious tree in Paradise. In classical literature, the height of beauty is compared to it.

Yazid(يزيد)-Yazid Ibn Muawiya, the second caliph of the Umayyads, who was an enemy of Imam Ali's (a.s.) descendants. In 680, he issued an order for his Imam Husayn's murder in the countryside of Karbala.

Yusifi-Kanan(يوسف كنعان)-Prophet Yagub's (pbuh) son. His brothers threw him into a well out of envy, because his father loved him more than his other

sons. Rescued by the merchants, Yusuf was taken to Egypt and bought in the market by the ruler's vizier.

Zeynab(زينب)-granddaughter of Prophet Muhammad, daughter of Hazrat Ali (a.s.), sister of Imam Husayn (a.s.).

Zabihullah(ذبيح الله)-Prophet Ismail (pbuh) is meant. It means "sacrifice cutting in the way of God". In the work, Ajiz states that his father's name is *Zabihullah*.

Zillullah(ظلاله)-It means the shadow of God. A name given to kings in classical literature.

Zunnun(ذوالنون)-It is the epithet of Prophet Yunus (pbuh). It means "lord of the fish".

Zulfuqar(ذوالفقار)-the name of Imam Ali's (a.s.) sword. In Eastern literature, it is shown as a symbol of victory and glory.

Names of fictional characters

Bijan(بيژن)-According to the legend, he is the son of Ibn Gudarz from the daughter of the legendary hero Rustam Zal, and according to another legend, Rustam's nephew. He fell in love with Afrasiyab's daughter Manija, and Manija loved him, too. Unbeknown to his father, he kept him in the palace. Afrasiyab found out about this and imprisoned him in a well for 7 years. Rustam came in a merchant's clothes and rescued Bijan from the well with the help of Manija. Then he took him to Iran.

Ashkbus(اشكبوس)-One of the characters of *Shahnameh*. He fought against Rustam by Afrasiyab.

Faramarz(فرامرز)-Rustam's son, the main character of "Shahnamah".

Farhad(فرهاد)-One of the characters of Nizami's poem "Khosrow and Shirin". In Eastern literature, it is used as a selfless lover, as well as a symbol of power and strength.

Fartus(فرطوس)- One of the heroes who served in Afrasiyab's army.

Giv(گيو)-One of the knights in the *Shahnameh*. He is shown as Guderz's son and Rustam's son-in-law.

Hatam Tayi(حاتم طايي)- One of the leaders and poets of the Arab tribes who lived in the VI-VII centuries. He is considered one of the generous people of his time. In Eastern literature, he is used as a symbol of a person who is famous for his generosity.

Iraj(ايرج)-One of the epic characters of Ferdowsi's *Shahnameh*. He is Firdun's youngest son in Iranian mythology.

Qarun(قارون)-According to legend, a man famous for his abundance of wealth and also for his greed. Sources indicate that he lived during Prophet Musa's period. In Eastern literature, it is shown as a symbol of wealth and greed.

Qeys(قيس)-It's Majnun's first name is related to the Arabic words "miqyas, qiyas, *muqayisat*" (means "measure"). This word, which is a symbol of love in Eastern literature, is also used as the name of a mountain in epics.

Leyli(ليلى)-She is the character of the epics about "Leyli and Majnun" spread in the folklore of many Middle Eastern peoples. In written literature, the image of Leyli was first used by Nizami Ganjavi, and later it was used by poets who wrote works on the same subject under the influence of Nizami.

Loghman(لقمان)-The legendary doctor became famous as a person who knows the cure for every ailment. His name appears in Quran.

Majnun(مجنون)-He is the character of the epic "Leyli and Majnun".

Manija(منیژه)-Afrasiyab's daughter in Shahnameh.

Rakhsh(رخش)-It is the name of Rustam's horse in Shahnameh. According to legend, that horse had the strength of an elephant and was chosen for its loyalty to Rustam. No one could ride it except Rustam.

Ruyintan(رویانتان)-Afrasiyab's son in "Shahnameh".

Siyavush(سیاوش)-In Shahnameh, he is the son of Keikavus, the Shah of Iran. He was brought up by Rustam Zal. Sudaba, one of his father's wives, fell in love with him, but because she did not achieve her goal, she slandered Sayavush and was ordered to go through fire to prove his innocence. Sayavush survived the fire and ran to Turan. In Turan, he married Firangiz, daughter of Afrasiyab. Later, because he was suspicious of her, he had her head cut.

Sohrab(سهراب)-It is the name of Rustam's son in Shahnameh.

Shabdiz(شبدیز)-It is the name of Khosrow Parviz's black horse. This horse was gifted to him by Shirin. Shabdiz was not an ordinary horse. It originated from a black stone located in a cave under a church built of hardened stones at the foot of Mount Inhirag.

Shakar(شکر)-In Nizami Ganjavi's poem "Khosrow and Shirin", the real name of Khosrow's wife, he married after Maryam. It is often mentioned as a symbol of sugar in Eastern literature.

Shaghad(شقاد)-Rustam's stepbrother in the epic poem Shahnameh. According to the legend, Shagad killed Rustam by throwing him into a well.

Shirin(شیرین)-the main character of Nizami Ganjavi's poem "Khosrow and Shirin". In Eastern literature, she is written as a smart, careful and faithful woman character.

Tahamtan(تهمتان)-It is one of the epithets of the famous Rustam Zal in Shahnameh. It means "commander", "strong", "hero".

Zal(زال)-Rustam's father in Shahnameh.

Zuleykha(زلیخا)-According to religious traditions, the wife of the vizier of the Egyptian king who bought Yusif. She fell in love with Yusif because of his beauty, but Yusif rejected her. Therefore, she had Yusif imprisoned by slandering him. After the death of the Shah, Yusif came to power and married Zuleykha.

4) Poets, scientists and their works

Buzar Jamhar(بوزر جمهر)-A politician, writer, poet who lived in the palace of Sultan Masud Ghaznavi. His real name was Qasim Bin Ibrahim Bin Mansur Buzurgmehr Qaini.

Arjang(ارژنگ)-the book of the famous artist Mani. Mani tried to convince the people that this book came from heaven because of the extremely beautiful paintings.

Ibn Yamin(ابن یامین)-He is known as a master of qit'a in Middle Eastern poetry.

Mani(مانی)-He is considered the founder of Manichaeism. He gained fame as an artist, philosopher, doctor, and engineer.

Mansur Hallaj(منصور حلاج)-A great poet and philosopher who lived and created at the end of the 9th century and the beginning of the 10th century. This personality, whose real name is Hallaj Mansur Husayni, was executed in Baghdad for his Sufi ideas.

Sheikh Sanan(شیخ صنعان)-An epic written by the Sufi poet Faridaddin Attar, in the work "Mantiqu-teyr", describing the love of the Sufi sheikh Sanan for the daughter of the christian.

Toponyms

The branch of onomastics that studies the laws of formation, development, function, phonetic, lexical, and grammatical features of geographic-territorial names is called toponymics. "Toponym" is derived from the Greek words "topos"- (place, space, region) and "onim" (name), and is used in the meaning of special names of geographical places (5, p. 60).

Each nation creates most of its special words based on the lexical units of its native language. They express the essence of a certain sign, event, quality. Toponyms are closely related to geography and history as they indicate the names of places related to the land. These expressions contain themselves the history and ethnography of the people.

Toponyms are used in fiction for various purposes:

1. The name of the areas where the real event took place is kept as it was at the time of the description
2. Toponyms created later, which are the product of the author's literary imagination
3. In fiction, toponyms are used to express the name of the area related to a certain event.

4. Astronomical names are used at various points in classical works. The use of such onomastic names is due to enriching the poetic lexicon of the work. In the work, onomastic units play a special role in the formation of poetic figures such as simile, irony, metaphor, etc.

There are many geographical terms related to the description of events in Ajiz's "Divan". Place names used in the language of the work existed in Southern Azerbaijan approximately 150 years ago. As we know at the moment, the persianization process of place names of Turkish origin has been purposefully carried out in Southern Azerbaijan, so the names of those toponyms have been changed. These names are based on that material. The poet mentions the names of many geographical places related to the description of the events in his qit'a's beginning with the line "Ummalu mubashir olan ayani-Miyanj" and as if gives us documentary historical material. This also helps the reader to imagine the real geographical period in the fictional work.

While studying the toponyms used in Ajiz's "Divan", we encountered a number of interesting points and we would like to share information about them.

Qoymuş burada Kəbəni ol həcisi-gümrah,

Bilməm nə səbəb özgə yerə bağlamış eħram (1, p.18b).

In the verse given above, Ajiz uses the term Kaaba as a poetic toponym. Thus, the term Kaaba is expressed as a place of purity and holiness, and the poet does not consider it acceptable to leave such a place and rely on another place. In general, the names of holy places convey stylistic character in many poets' poems. From genius Fuzuli and his successors to Khatai, many poets approached the expression Kaaba in a poetic way.

Aghmiyan(اڭ ميان)-a village located in the north-east of Sarab.

Allahhaq(الله حق)-a village in Sarabda.

Ballija(باليجا)-a mountainous village located in the east of Mishkin.

Bulkan(بلوكان)-a village in Miyana.

Beybulaghi(بيگ بولاغی)-a village in Miyana.

Bərzənd(برزند)-a territorial unit subordinate to Mishkin.

Baytul-haram(بيت الحرم)-the Kaaba in Mecca and its surroundings.

Badaxshan(بدخشان)-a province located in the Pamirs, famous for its jewels. This expression is often found in fiction. Poets used this phrase in poetry when they wanted to make any comparison.

Xəcalətdən əraq çin-çin cəbinindən tökər dərya,
Düşər kani-Bədəxşan qeyrətə, bağrını qan eylər
(1, p.52b)

Bisuton(بيستون)-in Eastern literature, this mountain is associated with the character of Farhad. Farhad cut this stone according to Shirin.

Bichagh(بيچاق)-a village in Southern Azerbaijan

Bozgush(بوزگوش)-a mountain between Sarab and Miyana

Bukaran(بوکران)-a village in Southern Azerbaijan

Cheshmekesh(چشمه کش)-a village in Miyana district in Southern Azerbaijan. In some sources, a distorted version of this name is found in the form "Sarykamysht".

Chukhuryurt(چوخوریورت)-a village in Miyana.

Chugush(چوقوش)-is one of the villages of Sarab.

Jahanabad(جهاناباد)- one of the neighborhoods of Burujard city in Iran.

Jildabakhan(جلده باخان)-a village in the southeast of Sarab

Dashbulag(داشبولاغ)-a village located in the Miyana province of Southern Azerbaijan

Deylam(ديلم)-the name given to the northwestern part of Gilan province in Iran. It is also used in fiction in the meaning of "coarse haired slave".

Darbend(در بند)-was one of the historical and ancient cities of Azerbaijan. It is currently part of Russia.

Diyarbakir(دياربکر)- a city in the Anatolian region of Turkiye.

Dizci(ديزجی)-a village in Ghazvin with a very beautiful and mysterious nature.

Dizmar(ديزمار)-a village in Eastern Azerbaijan

Duzana(دوزنه)-a village located twenty-two kilometers southwest of Miyana.

Duzman(دوزمان)- a village in Southern Azerbaijan

Esparz(اسپرز)-a fortress in the mountainous area of Mazandaran.

Abargan(ابرغان)-a mountainous village located in Sarab.

Abhar(ابهر)-It's one of the biggest cities of Zanjan province.

Andabil(انديبل)-the name of a village located in the south of Ardabil.

Araf(عرف)-According to religious beliefs, it is a place between heaven and hell.

Ardayan(اردیان)-This village, currently known as the name Ardaha, is located 20 kilometers south-east of Sarab.

Arasbar(ارسبار)-In state documents, the real name is used in the form "Arazbari". Dehkhoda connects this word with "Araz" and the word "bar-sahil, qıraq". It is one of the villages of Garadagh. Currently, Garadagh is called Arasbaran.

Afzal(افضل)-a village in Miyana

Arshag(ارشاق)-It's considered one of the historical districts of Mishkin city.

Aygidagoz(ايگيده گوز)-a village in Miyana

Farkush(فرکوش)-It's the name of a village between Miyana and Sarab with a population of about a thousand people.

Farkhar(فرخار)-the name of a village in Khorasan. It is similar to Zanjan in nature.

Firdovsi-barin(فردوس برين)-an ancient garden located in the Elbrus mountains in the north of Iran. In classical oriental literature, it means high heaven.

Goghtapa(گوگ تپه)-one of the mountainous villages of Meshkin city.

Habash(حبش)-a country in Africa. It is currently called "Ethiopia". It is used as a symbol of darkness in Eastern literature.

Həris(هریس)-a mountainous village located in the south of Sarab.

Hənabənd(حنابند)-a village in Miyana.

Hanadan(حنادان)-a name of a village being subordinated to Bandar-Langa, located in the south of Hormuz province, Iran.

Hirvan(هیروان)-a village in Sarab.

Khaybar fort(قلعه خیبر)-Khaybar fort, located approximately 120 kilometers from the city of Medina, was of great strategic importance for Muslims. According to history, up to 20 thousand Jews settled within the walls of this strong fortress. They had their own fountains, palm groves and fields.

Khaybar fort is a fort that was taken by Hazrat Ali (a.s.) with great heroism.

Khallakh(خلخ)-It was the capital of Turan during the Arjasp Shah's period.

Khuten(ختن)- a city in northwestern Turkestan.

Ishratabad(عشر تاباد)- There are villages with this name in several regions of southern Azerbaijan, in Kerman, Qazvin, etc.

Kanduvan(کندوان)-a village with an ancient history in Tabriz. In historical sources, its real name is shown as "Gundogan".

Kangarlu(کنگرلو)-a territorial unit subordinate to Mishkin.

Kasalan(کسلان)-It's the name of a village located in Kanduvan part of the city of Miyana.

Gilan(گیلان)-a province in Iran. In the past, it was known as the name Deylam.

Galajuq(قلعه جوق)- according to the notes of the Iranian scientist Huseyn Duzghun, there was no village with this name in Azerbaijan. However, in the work, this phrase is given as the name of a village located in Sarab.

Garasu(قره سو)-It's the name of a river in Ardabil.

Kipchak(قپچاق)-a name given to the places between the Ural Mountains and the Volga River in the southeast of Russia.

Qirxhbulakh(قیرخبولاق)-It's a village in the territory of Southern Azerbaijan, subordinated to province Kanduvan with a population of 287 people. It is mentioned that there is a river called "Qirxhbulag" in this area, and that the name of this river is also mentioned as "Binaravan" in some sources.

Bir həddə edim Qırxbulağı cari gözümdən,
Ta eyləsün ol Çeşməkəşün daməni tər (1, p.44b).

Gizilagaj(قز لا عاچ)-a village in Southern Azerbaijan.

Mahin(مهین)-a village subordinated to Sarab.

Malvan(ملوان)-one of the provinces in Gilan.

Miyana, Miyanj(میانه، میانج)-It's one of the ancient cities of Azerbaijan. This city, founded as a village, was the center of the historical Garmarud district and once was a part of the Sarab Khanate.

Mughan(موغان)-an area that Shahseven tribes inhabited. It is located on the bank of Araz river. Nadir Shah Afshar came to the throne in this area.

Nemsa(نمسه)-this is how Austria was called in official documents during the Gajar period.

Nagabad(نقباد)- a village located in the north of Miyan.

Nikpey(نیکپی)-a village in a part of Zanjan. Currently, it has the status of a city.

Nudula(نودوله)-a village in Miyana.

Ojaguste(اوجاق اوسته)- a name of place in Southern Azerbaijan.

Oxyuruq(اویوروق)- a village in Southern Azerbaijan.

Ovghan(اوغان)-a name of the village in Sarab.

Ozumdil(اوزومدیل)-It's a district in the Garadagh district of Southern Azerbaijan.

Sarab(سراب)-It's one of the oldest cities of Southern Azerbaijan. Presumably, the foundation of the city was laid during the Sasanian period. Currently, there are more than 50 thousand people.

Siyah Mansur(سیه منصور)-a village near Miyana in Eastern Azerbaijan.

Sovmaa(صومعه)-1) village in Kaleybar-Ahar; 2) Chaharoymaq-Qaraagaj-Maragha; 3) Ahar-Huma; 4) Heris-Ahar

Shalghin(شالغین)-a name of the village located in the city of Sarab in southern Azerbaijan. The population of the village is about one thousand.

Shamlu(شاملو)-a village located in the city of Heris in Eastern Azerbaijan.

Talvar(تالوار)-taken from the name of two villages (Chaytalvar and Bulagtalvar) located in the city of Miyana in Southern Azerbaijan.

Tark(ترک)-one of the ancient and historical places of Miyana.

Tarim(طاریم)- It's one of the cities located in Zanjan province. It borders with Gilan, Qazvin and Ardabil.

Tugh or Tava(توق، تاولا)-It's the name of a village located in the southwest of the city of Miyana. The village is bordered by the villages of Aydogmush from the south and Kamardagh from the south-west.

Tur(طور)-a name of the mountain located in the Sina Peninsula between Arabia and Egypt. That mountain was the first place of conversation between Prophet Moses (pbuh) and God. Poets used the name of this legendary mountain in their works as a reference to religious belief, faith, as well as for certain poetic-stylistic purposes (4, p. 157).

Turan(توران)-a name given by the ancient Iranians to the parts of Turkestan and Tataristan. In "Shahnameh", Turan is the opposite of Iran. This place is called Turan because it has been the abode of Turkic tribes since ancient times.

In Ajiz's divan has a sufficient number of toponyms related to religious names. The use of toponyms such as Mecca, Medina, Karbala, Tur, Khorasan, Baghdad, Kanan etc. in the work embodies the poet's great respect for our holy religion.

Təxti- zindani-bəlayə məni saldı bəxtim,
Yoxdu, bir canibi-Kən'anə gedəm naqəsəvar (1, p.91a).

When looking at a verse in Ajiz's qasida, we see that Kanan denotes a geographical location. However, since the sanctity of this geographical name is related to the prophet Yusif, in other poems, the toponym Kanan is no longer a geographical name, but means a holy person.

Qoyub ta çün əyağımı ləbü lə'li-Züleyxayə,
Deyün, vəsli-Züleyxadən Kən'an alub kamı (1, p. 136a).

Tus(طوس)- an ancient city in Iran.

Tukuldan(توکولدان)-a village subordinated to Sarab.

Uchtapa(اوچ تپه)-a village in Miyana.

Vanjan(ونجان)-one of the villages of Garmarudi.

Yengija(یئگیجه)-a name of a village located in the Marivan region of Iran.

Yikhind(بیخند)-a name of a fortress located in Ghazvin.

Zablistan(زابلیستان)-in Ferdowsi's work Shahnameh, a settlement near the Hamun River near the eastern border of Iran.

Zangbar(زنگبار)-an island in the Indian Ocean on the east coast of Africa. There is also a city of this name in the west of that island. Currently, this area is included in Tanzania. Zangbar is more famous for its cloves.

Zurabad(زورآباد)-a name of place in Southern Azerbaijan.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the research of onomastic units in Ajiz's divan determines the individual style of the poet. The richness of these units means the richness of the artistic

style of the work. Also, the use of onomastic names increases the poetic-imagery in the work. This also plays an important role in the creation of simile, metaphors, exaggerations, and symbols as means of artistic expression.

On the other hand, presented of the ancient village names belonging to Southern Azerbaijan by Ajiz in writing form, ensures that they will be passed on to future generations, and at the same time, they will be one of the ancient places of our native Azerbaijan.

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